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ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES.

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Abstract. This article examines the competitiveness of an enterprise in the market, the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy, the policy of moving goods in the market, pricing policy and its analysis, analysis of product distribution policy, the policy of moving goods in the market, the complexity of potential consumer behavior, and the development of human resources.

Keywords: Enterprise, market, goods, price, potential consumers, modernization, innovation.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada korxonaning bozordagi raqobatbardoshligi uning bozorga yo'naltirilgan siyosatining samaradorligi, tovarni bozorda siljitish siyosati, narx siyosati va uning tahlili, tovar tarqatish siyosatining tahlili, tovarni bozorda siljitish siyosati, potentsial iste'molchilar xulq atvorini murakkablashishi, inson resurslarini rivojlantirish ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Korxonona, bozor, tovar, narx, potentsial iste'molchilar, modernizatsiya, innovatsiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются конкурентоспособность предприятия на рынке, эффективность его рыночно-ориентированной политики, политика реализации товаров на рынке, ценовая политика и ее анализ, анализ политики распределения продукции, политика реализации товаров на рынке, сложность поведения потенциальных потребителей и развитие человеческих ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: Предприятие, рынок, товары, цена, потенциальные потребители, модернизация, инновации.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the urgent issues are to increase the range and quality of goods produced, ensure their stable sales in domestic and foreign markets, increase competitiveness in a highly competitive environment, extend the life of goods, create new product designs based on market demand, strengthen the position of local goods, and ensure their brand recognition.

The main goal of the "Strategy for the Development of Competition in Commodity and Financial Markets for 2020-2024" established by our President is to stimulate economic growth and innovation, increase investment flows, and create new jobs by creating effectively functioning markets and a healthy competitive environment. This is also aimed at developing relations between economic entities.¹

The rise of market relations to a new level requires the scientific organization of marketing activities in enterprises, the widespread promotion of marketing management principles. Considering the great tasks facing exporting enterprises today, it is possible to confirm the relevance of the topic.

Currently, the expansion of exports opens up new opportunities for ensuring economic growth, increasing production efficiency, creating new jobs and improving the living standards of the population. We know that in recent years, Uzbekistan has seen a significant increase in the foreign trade economy of enterprises and an improvement in the export structure. The role of export-oriented enterprises in the growth of foreign trade and export potential and, as a result, in strengthening the competitiveness of the national economy is increasing.

In the development of society, each participant in market relations develops the skills to evaluate their economic activities, conclude contracts related to foreign economic activity, select partners, use international marketing principles in their activities, make decisions based on them, and become a powerful factor in increasing production efficiency and producing competitive products on the world market. Since the research conducted today is based on a marketing approach, we comprehensively scientifically and methodologically study such concepts as export potential, export production, export opportunities, and export specialization,

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6019 dated July 6, 2020. [Decree](#)»On additional measures to further develop the competitive environment and reduce state participation in the economy»

and assess their place in our national economy. At the same time, it is intended to reveal the theoretical and practical essence of export-oriented production and pay attention to its place in the international division of labor.

It should also be noted that without modern knowledge, new techniques and technologies, it is impossible to achieve success in the market. Therefore, mastering knowledge related to economic management, organization of production, research of the global and domestic market situation, supply and demand relations, modern management and marketing is becoming a requirement today.

Review of literature on the topic. Based on foreign experience, it should be noted that the competitiveness of an enterprise in the market is determined by the effectiveness of its market-oriented policy. Many economists have been engaged in the development and application of marketing principles. Among them, we can include such famous scientists as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, A. Marshall.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R. Ibragimov, YO. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, D. Rakhimova, D. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva and others.

At the same time, it should be noted that methodological work on the practical application of theoretical developments and their application in enterprises is insufficient. In order to apply theoretical recommendations in practice, each enterprise must draw on its own experience, conduct relevant scientific research, and develop recommendations and systems for implementing the theory.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

From this point of view, the effective use of marketing activities is one of the most important issues in further improving the efficiency of industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan. Therefore, the problem of adapting and developing marketing methods and tools to local conditions is becoming urgent for the enterprises of our Republic. For this, it is necessary to thoroughly study the methodology of conducting market research.

The analysis of marketing management is carried out in accordance with the marketing mix concept presented in the theoretical part of our study, namely: product (product range), price (pricing policy), place (sales organization) and promotion (marketing communications). In addition, when analyzing marketing management, we also separately considered the company's policy towards employees.

The development of the product range is the most important function of enterprise marketing. It is manifested in the application of traditional or latent technical and material capabilities of the manufacturer to products and services that have a certain consumer value, satisfy the buyer and bring profit to the enterprise.

The product range of the SAG joint venture includes various carpets, rugs, carpeting and other types of upholstery, differing in their composition, production technology, density, pile length, size, appearance, design and other technical parameters.

Today, in order to expand the range of carpets sold in the markets of the republic and meet consumer demand, the SAG joint venture has launched the production of carpets of more than 3,000 designs, which are part of about 30 collections. These include the collections «Tumaris», «Zilli», «Rodin», «Zara», «Troya», «Iron», «Sheikh», «Pantera», «Shohsultan», «Imperial», «Avangard», «Super Shaggy», «Isfahan», «Avangard», «Babi», «Imperial Coffee», etc. The collections here are diverse in design. Carpets are produced in different colors, mainly 8 colors, and therefore the design of the collections differs from each other (Table 1).

Table 1

«SAG» Assessing the importance of LLC products for the company

Collection name	In revenue share	In a growth pattern	Grouping
Isfahan	19.45%	19.45%	A
Tumaris	18.39%	37.84%	A
Rodin Gray	11.40%	49.24%	A
Zilly	9.86%	59.1%	A

Emir	6.98%	66.08%	A
Ponte	5.24%	71.32%	A
Reflex	4.62%	75.94%	A
Therapy	4.61%	80.55%	B
Avant-garde	2.89%	83.44%	B
Baby	2.87%	86.31%	B
X(20 others)	13.69%	100%	BC
General	100.00%		

In our case, group A (15-80% by law) Sheikh, Imperial, Iran, Aladin, Almira, Zara, Fortuna (23% of the assortment) accounted for 75.94% of the total revenue, group B and group C Super Shaggy, Troya, Imperial Gray and 20 other collections accounted for the rest of the revenue. It is clear from this that the collections in group A are the main sources of revenue for the enterprise.

By dividing products into such groups, a company can have a report that identifies exactly which group of goods is the main source of income.

«SAG» LLC products in the company's income. Another area of focus is the shape and color combination of carpets. In recent years, we have introduced the production of carpets of any size, depending on the wishes of the carpet maker, that is, we have introduced work on individual orders. Today, our task is to introduce the production of carpets of various shapes (round, oval, complex shapes). This will allow us to fully satisfy the design requirements of consumers.

Another aspect of the product policy is to increase the density of carpet weaving, that is, to increase the softness and functionality of carpets. In this direction, the company's management can be seen as pursuing a policy aimed at modernizing production. Today, investment projects are being worked on to further improve production. Areas such as increasing the types of yarns used in carpets, ensuring color fastness, and expanding the range of carpet products are also separate aspects of the policy of improving the quality of our products.

Developed market relations cannot exist without innovation, therefore the enterprise pays great attention to scientific research and strives to implement the results of scientific research.

«SAG» The pricing policy of the LLC is based on the functional purpose of the products produced and the purpose of the purchase. In this case, the division of the company's products into categories is the main criterion for determining their price.

Category A: Products that confirm the status of the consumer, are recognized as home decoration, are made of high-quality raw materials and have individual characteristics. These products are usually part of a collection and are aimed at satisfying the needs of each consumer;

Category B: products made from high-quality raw materials, distinguished by their design, but containing batches of products that conform to mass design and fashion, and aimed at the upper and middle income strata of the population;

Category C: Carpet products that are mass-produced to meet the needs of the population. Their main characteristics are their focus on the needs of the majority of consumers, the balance of price and quality, and the speed of order fulfillment.

Category D. Carpets and bedding products manufactured for public places, enterprises and organizations.

For each category of products "Sam Antep Kilam" JV The LLC company develops its own pricing policy. The prices for some of the products manufactured by the company in 2025 are presented in the table below (Table 2).

Table 2.

Market price of carpets of «SAG» LLC as of July 1, 2024

t/r	Collection name	VAT you	With VAT (retail price)
1	Isfahan	373300	485300
2	Tumaris	324700	422050
3	Rodin Gray	243300	316250
4	Zilly	132200	158700
5	Emir	133300	160000
6	Ponte	248000	330050
7	Reflex	135600	165600

8	Therapy	243300	316250
9	Avant-garde	99700	119600
10	Baby	99700	119700

When developing the company's pricing policy, attention is paid mainly to the prices of competitors, while on the other hand, it is indicated that the company works in accordance with the agreed terms with partners in the republic and abroad.

SAG LLC is a leader in the carpet market in all aspects. Today, its carpet products are sold in more than 500 points of sale throughout Uzbekistan.

In each region, the «SAG» LLC enterprise has its own official dealers and stores, the number of which is more than 20. (...-table) Dealers are located in almost all major cities of the republic: Tashkent, Samarkand, Navoi, Bukhara, Urgench, Nukus, Karshi, Termez, Namangan, Andijan, Fergana, Kokand, Jizzakh, Gulistan (Table 3).

Table 3

Official dealers and stores of "SAG" LLC

No.	City name	Store name	Address
1	Tashkent	«THE WORLD OF SAG CARPETS»	Kuksaroy Street, Takhta Bazaar
2		«SAG CARPETS»	TXY, Bek-tupi Shopping Complex
3		«SAG»	Kushbegi area, KXY street 14
4		«SAG»	Chinabad, Bardavom Street 27
5		«IDEA HOME»	TXY Street, Med Gorodok
6		«SAG»	Chilonzor, Bogiston Street 4A
7	Samarkand	«SAG»	Rudaki Street 229
8	Navoi	«SAG»	Victory King Power, 197
9	Bukhara	«SAG»	Khujandurabad Street, 11
10	Urgench	«SAG»	Selfless 1 house 1
11	Nukus	«SAG»	J.Aimirzaeva, 93
12	Against	«SAG»	Uzbekistan Street 405
13	Termez	«SAG»	Progress 47A
14	Namangan	«SAG»	Girvonsay, 11
15	Andijan	"SAG" Kashmir store	Independence 21
16		«SAG»	Kusharik Dasakhi Street 1
17	Fergana	«SAG»	Joydam Street 24
18	Kokand	«SAG»	A.Novoi Street 147A
19	Jizzah	«SAG»	Quiet market
20	Gulistan	«SAG»	Neighborhood

The advertising and communication policy of SAG LLC is aimed at providing consumers with more information. In this regard, electronic media are primarily used, the company's website (<https://www.sag.uz/uz>),

Telegram, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter. The company also pays great attention to outdoor advertising. Given the functions and features of carpet products, the company pays great attention to expanding relations with wholesale buyers. Communication policy is one of the main tasks of the enterprise's marketing department. The joint venture «SAG» LLC also seeks to establish trading houses abroad. For example, on March 9, 2024 The opening ceremony of the «SAG» Uzbek carpet and «Gulnor» silk products trading house was held in New York City. According to the Embassy of Uzbekistan in the United States, this trading house is the second Uzbek national light industry products exhibition space in the United States, after a similar shopping center opened in Philadelphia in 2020.

SAG LLC pays special attention to the issue of personnel development. This can be seen from the information presented in the table below (Table 4)

Table 4
Employee support program at SAG LLC in 2025

Expense items	Measures included	Value
Seminars and trainings	Organization of staff training, training, seminars	30 million soums
Company loyalty programs	Providing bonuses to employees with 10, 15, 16 years of experience	25 million soums
	KPI Bonus	180 million soums
	Sick leaves	26.5 million soums
	Maternity leave	16.3 million soums
Medical service	Periodic examination of employees and health restoration programs at the Bionur Med Service medical center.	50 million soums
Eating	Organizing free meals for employees	3.5 billion soums
Transportation	Transporting employees to their workplaces by company transport	500 million soums
	Entertainment	95 million soums
	EH&S costs	40 million soums
Total costs		4.462 billion soums 4,960 million soums
Cost per employee		

The company takes certain measures to ensure the safety of employees. For example: All workers and employees are fully provided with special clothing at the company's expense; All employees are fully provided with personal protective equipment. Especially during the quarantine period, great attention was paid to protecting the health of employees;

Providing workers with milk and dairy products in accordance with standards; Providing workers and employees with full supplies of detergents; Fully covering the costs of labor protection and safety equipment at the expense of the enterprise, etc.

In addition, all benefits and health restoration measures specified in the public contract are also financed by the enterprise.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

To summarize: the results of the analyses conducted showed that «SAG» LLC has developed a unique approach to marketing management, namely, to outperform competitors in technological and technical aspects and to guarantee product quality. This approach, which has been effective since the company was founded, continues to contribute significantly to the company's success in the carpet sales market today.

However, today, the sharp changes in the national and foreign market conditions and the complexity of potential consumer behavior are creating a development gap in marketing activities. This requires increased attention to customer communication, sales and post-sales processes.

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